

Your Operating System for Risk and Compliance

Governance, risk and compliance (GRC) software for businesses and advisors that's easy to use, includes all the content you need and is powered by artificial intelligence to help get you audit-ready and in control faster than ever before.

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About us

[6clicks](#) is helping businesses and service providers bring risk assessment, risk management and compliance processes into the digital era.

Our accessible tool allows businesses to digitally integrate service providers into these existing processes. We want to foster trust and transparency within and outside organisations, backed by new technologies and direct digital guidance.